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Profiles of Susceptibility of Adolescents to Socially Unacceptable Extreme Discourses (SUEDs)

Work package 2 – Deliverable 2.2

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	4
2. About DEMINE	5
3. Introduction	7
4. Methodology.....	8
Young adults.....	8
4.1.1 Procedure and sample	8
4.1.2 Measures.....	8
4.1.3 Analysis	9
Adolescents.....	9
4.2.1 HateLess – original intervention and Italian adaptation.....	10
4.2.2 Procedure and sample	10
4.2.3 Measures.....	10
4.2.4 Data Handling and Analysis.....	11
5. Results	12
Susceptibility to Extreme Discourse among Young People	12
5.1.1 Young adults.....	12
5.1.1.1 Sample Characteristics and Variable Overview	12
5.1.1.2 Associations Between Exposure, Susceptibility Factors, and Outcomes.....	12
5.1.1.3 Exposure and Individual Characteristics as Predictors of Outcomes.....	13
5.1.1.4 Susceptibility as a Moderator: Does Individual Vulnerability Amplify Exposure Effects?	14
5.1.2 Adolescents.....	15
5.1.2.1 Variable overview	15
5.1.2.2 Associations Between Exposure, Individual Factors and Responses to Hate Speech ..	15
5.2 Susceptibility to Intervention Measures in Adolescence.....	16
6. Conclusion and Recommendations.....	18
6.2 Susceptibility to Intervention Measures in Adolescence.....	20
6.3 Overall conclusion and recommendations	21
7. References.....	22
8. Appendices.....	24
A. Measurement Items Study 1	24
B. Questionnaire Study 2	27
C. Tables	31

1. Executive Summary

Extreme discourse poses a growing threat to interpersonal communication, social cohesion and psychological well-being, both online and offline. This report focuses specifically on hate speech as one form of socially unacceptable extreme discourse, examining how young people may differ in their vulnerability to such discourse and in their responsiveness to prevention efforts.

To do so, the report combines data from two studies conducted with young Italians. The first is an online survey examining young adults' exposure to migration-related hateful content and its associations with attitudinal and behavioural outcomes. The second is a pilot implementation of a school-based intervention, examining adolescents' online hate speech involvement at baseline and exploring whether intervention outcomes differed according to psychological traits, prior experiences, and sociodemographic characteristics.

In both studies susceptibility is not treated as a stable individual characteristic. Instead, it is understood as a reaction inclination shaped by environmental factors, psychological dispositions, sociodemographic background, and past experiences. The findings indicate that susceptibility differs depending on developmental stage and research design.

Among young adults, heightened exposure to migration-related harmful content was linked to stronger activism and radicalism intentions as well as somewhat more positive stereotype warmth towards immigrants. Personal beliefs and competences significantly shaped these associations. Particularly right-wing authoritarianism was found to be a central susceptibility factor. Young adults high in right-wing authoritarianism displayed a stronger connection between exposure and radicalism intentions, while those low in right-wing authoritarianism did not exhibit this influence. In contrast, cognitive flexibility was related to lower desensitisation and radicalism intentions suggesting that it serves as a protective factor. These findings indicate that young adults' vulnerability to extreme discourse can differ due to dispositional risk factors.

Adolescents reported little involvement in online hate speech, particularly in terms of perpetration and victimisation. Defending behaviour of others who became targets of hate speech displayed the most prominent and consistent associations, including positive correlations with empathy, self-efficacy, sense of responsibility, media literacy, and factual hate speech knowledge. This pattern suggests that bystander counter speech is reinforced by a combination of emotional, motivational and cognitive factors. The pilot adaptation of the intervention proved efficacious in increasing factual hate speech knowledge and media literacy. Exploratory moderation analyses suggested that some intervention-related gains may have been stronger among specific groups, including boys, students with an immigrant background, students from lower-affluence families, and adolescents with prior involvement in hate speech dynamics. Given the pilot design, non-randomised classroom assignment, and small sample size, these findings should be interpreted cautiously. These findings imply that interventions may be particularly beneficial for adolescents already exposed to greater social and structural vulnerabilities highlighting the relevant equity-related outcomes.

Taken together, the findings from both studies demonstrate that susceptibility cannot be defined by a singular stable risk profile. Instead, it is composed of a combination of prior experience, a variety of skills, and sociodemographic background. Intervention efforts should be aimed at training necessary competencies while accounting for individual differences among young people including their situational vulnerabilities.

2. About DEMINE

DEMINE goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political, and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research, and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work, and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration, and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.
- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyse the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media, and interpersonal communication.

- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.
- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers, and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarisation and radicalisation to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarised world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute, and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium will train nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills, and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

Extreme discourse has become a growing challenge to social interactions and individuals' mental health both online and offline (Madriaza et al., 2025). Young people are at increased risk to such discourse due to their heightened tendency to take risks, limited lived experiences, and environmental influences such as peer pressure (Steinberg, 2016). In combination with existing societal attitudes, growing autonomy and identity formation, and changes in social surroundings might leave certain adolescents more vulnerable to facing extreme discourse than others. Understanding which subgroups are particularly susceptible to extreme discourse as well as preventative interventions is essential to supporting those at risk and, thus, limiting existing and future extreme discourse. Therefore, this report has two main objectives:

- 1) Identifying individuals or groups among young people that are more vulnerable to extreme discourse than their peers,
- 2) Understanding which individuals or groups among adolescents are more receptive to prevention measures.

While extreme discourse encompasses a range of phenomena, the present report focuses specifically on hate speech as one prominent form of socially unacceptable extreme discourse, particularly in online contexts, as it constitutes one of the most prevalent and empirically studied forms of antagonistic communication with direct relevance to intergroup relations, social cohesion, and adolescents' everyday media environments. This focus allows for a more precise examination of how young people are exposed to, affected by, and respond to such content. To do so, the report features data from two studies. The first is an online survey concentrating on young adults' exposure to extreme discourse online. The second is a quasi-experimental pre-post control group intervention study targeting hate speech among adolescents. To identify particularly vulnerable individuals or groups of young people, exposure to extreme discourse among young adults as well as involvement in online extreme discourse among adolescents were analysed with regard to sensitivity to outside stimuli and personal or demographic traits using both studies. Subsequently, susceptibility to prevention was measured by exploring the effect of personal traits and identity on measured outcomes in the intervention study.

Susceptibility is understood here as a relational and context-dependent concept rather than a fixed individual trait. The two studies operationalise susceptibility differently because they address different parts of the same broader process. In Study 1, susceptibility refers to whether psychological and sociodemographic characteristics strengthen or weaken associations between exposure to migration-related hate speech and attitudinal or behavioural outcomes. In Study 2, susceptibility is examined in two ways: first, through baseline associations with adolescents' involvement in online hate speech; and second, through exploratory differences in responsiveness to the HateLess intervention. This distinction is important because baseline vulnerability, exposure effects, and intervention responsiveness are not equivalent indicators of susceptibility. Instead, they represent related but analytically distinct ways in which young people may be differentially affected by or responsive to hate speech. These varying conceptualisations of susceptibility illustrate their different purposes (exposure vs. intervention effects) but are still comparable due to both defining susceptibility not as one specific trait, but as individual response patterns based on one's experience, background, and environment.

While most researchers agree that adolescents are particularly vulnerable to extreme discourse, definitions of this developmental stage vary widely. Contemporary frameworks place it roughly between ages 10 and 19, with some extending it to 24 (Sawyer et al., 2018). To ensure clarity, in the present research participants aged 18-25 are referred to as young adults, whereas those aged 13-16 are classified as adolescents. This report focuses on these two age groups as they differ in vulnerability to outside influences, parental control, and social media usage. As the young adult study introduces the conceptual and analytical approach to susceptibility, it is presented first. The adolescent study then builds on the established framework extending it to a younger population and intervention effects.

4. Methodology

Young adults

4.1.1 Procedure and sample

The data for this analysis come from the first wave of a larger longitudinal study on susceptibility to and the impact of socially unacceptable extreme discourses (SUEDs). Data were collected through an online survey administered between 9th of January 2026 and 13th of February 2026. Participants were recruited with the help of the panel company Bilendi, and the sample was representative of the Italian population with respect to age, educational level, and gender.

In total, 2,991 completed the survey (response rate relative to the panel invite 34.4%). For the present analysis, the sample was restricted to Italian young adults aged 18 to 25 years, resulting in a final analytic sample of 245 participants. While this sample size is sufficient for main effect estimation, statistical power for detecting interaction effects is limited and moderation findings should be interpreted with caution. The mean age of the sample was 22.95 years ($SD = 1.84$), and 35.5% of participants were male and 64.5% female. In terms of education about half of participants (50.2%) reported upper secondary education as their highest completed degree, while 42.0% reported higher education. Only very small shares reported primary education (0.4%), lower secondary education (1.6%), post-secondary non-higher education (5.3%), or a doctorate (0.4%). Regarding household financial situation, nearly half of participants (47.8%) indicated that they got by fine, meaning they had enough for everyday needs but needed to save for larger expenses, while 30.6% reported that they lived well, being able to afford most things without saving for them. Smaller proportions reported that they lived modestly (14.3%), lived very well (4.1%), or struggled to get by (3.3%).

4.1.2 Measures

The key independent variable was self-reported **exposure to hateful migration-related content on social media**, measured with a single item assessing how often participants encountered hateful or hostile posts about migrants (adapted from Soral et al., 2018). As a single-item self-report measure, it captures perceived or recognised exposure rather than objective content exposure and is limited in its reliability and construct coverage compared to multi-item scales. It should therefore be interpreted accordingly (see Appendix A for full wording and response scales for all measures).

Three susceptibility characteristics were included. **Sensory processing sensitivity** (SPS; Pluess et al., 2023) captures the tendency to process environmental and social stimuli deeply, with heightened awareness and emotional reactivity. Individuals high in SPS may be more strongly affected by

emotionally charged content such as hate speech, making it a relevant marker of differential vulnerability. **Cognitive flexibility** (CFS; Martin & Rubin, 1995) reflects the capacity to consider multiple perspectives and adapt behaviour across situations. As a trainable cognitive skill, it is of particular interest as a potential protective factor against the normalisation of hateful content. **Right-wing authoritarianism** (RWA; Bizumic & Duckitt, 2018) reflects dispositional orientations toward authority, social order, and norm enforcement. Given its established links to outgroup hostility and receptivity to norm-violating content, it represents a dispositional risk factor worth examining in the context of SUED exposure. All three were measured using validated scales and showed good internal consistency ($\alpha = .83, .84, \text{ and } .78$, respectively).

Five outcome variables were assessed. **Desensitisation** captured the degree to which individuals report diminished emotional reactions to hateful migration content online ($\alpha = .89$). Emotional numbing to hate speech is concerning as it may lower the threshold for accepting or reproducing such content over time. **Stereotypes** (Asbrock, 2010) toward immigrants were modelled across two dimensions: *competence* ($\alpha = .79$) and *warmth* ($\alpha = .90$), reflecting cognitive and affective components of outgroup perception respectively. These dimensions are relevant as hateful content often targets both the perceived capabilities and the humanity of migrants. **Activism and radicalism intentions** (ARIS; Moskalenko & McCauley, 2009) assessed willingness to engage in conventional advocacy versus more extreme actions in relation to immigration issues ($\alpha = .88 \text{ and } .92$). Distinguishing between these two forms of behavioural intention is important for identifying whether exposure to SUEDs mobilises prosocial engagement or contributes to more concerning radicalisation pathways. **Affective polarisation** measured sympathy toward individuals holding opposing views on migration, assessed via a feeling thermometer, which is an adaptation of a widely used measure in comparative research (Gidron et al., 2022).

Background variables included age, gender, education, subjective socioeconomic status, political orientation, migration background, and contact with immigrants from EU and non-EU countries ($r = .67$).

In this study, susceptibility is defined as the extent to which individual characteristics (both psychological dispositions and sociodemographic factors) are associated with stronger or weaker responses to hateful migration-related content.

4.1.3 Analysis

Descriptive statistics and bivariate Pearson correlations were first computed to characterise the sample and examine associations among variables. Main effects were then estimated using multiple linear regression, with each outcome modelled separately as a function of hateful content exposure alongside sociodemographic and susceptibility covariates. To examine whether susceptibility characteristics moderated the association between exposure and outcomes, a series of moderation models were estimated by introducing interaction terms between mean-centred exposure and each susceptibility variable (SPS, CFS, RWA) in turn. For the significant interaction, simple slopes analysis was conducted to probe the effect of exposure at low (-1 SD), mean, and high ($+1 \text{ SD}$) levels of the moderator.

Adolescents

4.2.1 HateLess – original intervention and Italian adaptation

The HateLess intervention was designed to reduce involvement in online hate speech and to promote counter-speech by enhancing cognitive and emotional skills among 7th to 9th graders (Wachs et al., 2023). It was originally implemented as a project week of 30 hours at German schools. The schools' teaching staff facilitated the intervention based on a manual and materials provided at www.hateless.de. The programme is divided into five modules of six hours each focusing on the definition, causes, and consequences of hate speech as well as counter strategies and a creative reflection project. The intervention has been found to increase empathy, self-efficacy, and hate speech countering among participating adolescents (Wachs et al., 2023, 2024, 2025a, 2025b).

The data used for this report are derived from the pilot study of a version of the HateLess intervention translated and adapted to the Italian school context by DC5. This pilot study was implemented from October to December 2025, with the main study scheduled for late 2026 to early 2027. The adapted intervention consists of five in-person sessions of two consecutive 55-minute school hours each. The pilot study was conducted by two trained facilitators – a research assistant, who is a licensed psychologist, and a master's student in psychology – with all first-year classes in an upper secondary school in Northern Italy. The school offered vocational, technical, and high school degree branches. The content and format of the adaptation were kept as close as possible to the original while accounting for feasibility and cultural differences.

4.2.2 Procedure and sample

The pilot study was pre-registered on PROSPERO (DOI: 10.17605/OSF.IO/FT48V) and received ethical approval from the ethics committee of the School of Psychology of the University of Padua (protocol n. 1366-a). Intervention procedures, content, and data handling were presented to teachers and parents in two separate online sessions and to students in-person during class hours. Informed consent was obtained from participants and parents. It was available in the nine most common languages spoken in the school community. The pre- and post-test questionnaires were administered one week before the first intervention session and one week after the last one. Questionnaires were provided online and as paper-versions in the six languages most spoken among the student body.

The sample consisted of 167 adolescents in nine classrooms. Four classrooms were assigned to the control group and five to the experimental group. Those in the control group attended their usual lessons, while the experimental classrooms participated in the adapted HateLess intervention.

Sixteen participants were excluded from analysis due to missing or incomplete responses to one or both surveys. Thus, the final sample comprised 151 participants – 64 in the control ($M_{age} = 14.00$, $SD = .68$) and 87 in the experimental group ($M_{age} = 13.94$, $SD = .56$). The overall mean age was 13.97 ($SD = .63$). In the experimental condition, 43 students (49.4%) were female, 41 (47.1%) male, two (2.3%) selected other and one (1.1%) did not indicate gender. The control group included 39 male (60.9%) and 25 female students (39.1%). Thirty-eight (43.7%) students in the experimental group had an immigrant background and 15 (23.4%) in the control group. Family affluence in both conditions was on the lower-medium side based on the Family Affluence Scale, with a mean of 8.26 ($SD = 2.04$, $range = 4-13$) in the experimental and 8.42 ($SD = 1.91$, $range = 3-13$) in the control group.

4.2.3 Measures

The key independent variable was participation in the intervention, operationalised as condition (experimental vs. control).

Susceptibility characteristics included psychological dispositions and sociodemographic factors that may shape adolescents' baseline involvement in and responsiveness to hate speech and intervention content. **Sensory processing sensitivity** was measured using the Highly Sensitive Child scale (Pluess et al., 2018; $\alpha = .61$). It consists of twelve items divided into three subscales: Ease of Excitation (EOE; 5 items), Aesthetic Sensitivity (AES; 4 items), Low Sensory Threshold (LST; 3 items). To assess **empathy** for victims of hate speech ($\alpha = .87$), an adaptation of Knauf et al.'s (2018) 6-item empathy scale by Wachs et al. (2023) was used. Participants also reported **sociodemographic information**, including age, gender, immigrant background, parental education, and family affluence. To assess immigrant background, students were asked to indicate their own and their parents' birth country. Those who were born outside of Italy or had a parent born abroad were classified as having an immigrant background. Parental education was evaluated separately for mother and father. Students' socio-economic background was assessed using the 6-item "Family Affluence Scale" (FAS III; Hartley et al., 2016; adapted by Wachs et al., 2023).

Outcome variables captured adolescents' involvement in hate speech as well as cognitive, emotional, and behavioural competencies targeted by the intervention. Following a brief definition of hate speech, participants responded to three items about their **online hate speech involvement** (Wachs et al., 2024). The measure comprised three single-item indicators of hate speech involvement: perpetration, defending, victimisation. **Media literacy** was assessed using the 6-item "Subjective social media literacy" subscale of the Youth Social Media Literacy Scale (Purington Drake et al., 2023; $\alpha = .72$). To measure **factual hate speech knowledge**, a 5-item scale developed by Wachs et al. (2024) was employed ($\alpha = .80$). Adolescents' **critical reflection skills** were assessed employing the subscale "Factor 1: Recognition of social inequity" of the Critical Reflection Scale (Chan, 2022; $\alpha = .72$). To measure **counter speech**, a 4-item scale by Wachs et al. (2023) was employed ($\alpha = .74$). **Self-efficacy** was measured with a scale developed by Knauf et al. (2018; $\alpha = .72$). It consisted of three items. Another scale by Knauf et al. (2018) was used to evaluate participants' **sense of responsibility** comprising of three items ($\alpha = .77$).

4.2.4 Data Handling and Analysis

Each participant was assigned an individual ID to maintain anonymity. Responses from those who failed to respond to both questionnaires as well as duplicate and incomplete contributions ($n = 16$) were removed ($n = 16$).

The analysis was performed in SPSS and R. First, bivariate associations between hate speech involvement and psychological factors (e.g., empathy, self-efficacy) at pretest were explored. Next, to assess whether individual characteristics were associated with differential intervention outcomes, post-test outcomes were modelled as a function of condition (experimental vs. control) while controlling for the respective pre-test scores. Based on theoretical considerations, SPS and empathy were included as candidate moderators, as they reflect individual differences in responsiveness to emotional and social stimuli. We focused on three cognitive outcomes: media literacy skills, factual knowledge of hate speech, and critical reflection. All continuous variables were mean-centred prior to analyses. Additional exploratory analyses examined whether intervention-related changes differed by selected sociodemographic characteristics and prior hate speech involvement. These analyses

included gender, immigrant background, family affluence, and baseline perpetration or victimisation. They were treated as exploratory and are therefore interpreted cautiously rather than as equivalent indicators of susceptibility.

5. Results

Susceptibility to Extreme Discourse among Young People

5.1.1 Young adults

5.1.1.1 Sample Characteristics and Variable Overview

Descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1. Overall, participants reported moderate levels of exposure to hateful migration content and most outcome variables. Like majority of outcome variables, activism intentions were moderate, whereas radicalism intentions were comparatively lower, which is expected as it is less likely to be willing to take violent actions than engage in more traditional activism.

Susceptibility-related characteristics (SPS, CFS, and RWA) were generally around the midpoint of their respective scales, indicating sufficient variability for subsequent analyses.

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Age	22.95	1.84	18	25
Political orientation	5.7	2.35	1	11
Exposure to hateful migration content	3.47	1.68	1	7
Sensory processing sensitivity	4.59	0.9	1	7
Cognitive flexibility	4.08	0.63	2.5	6
Right-wing authoritarianism	3.47	1.07	1	6.5
Desensitisation	3.24	1.28	1	7
Stereotype competence	3.91	1.22	1	7
Stereotype warmth	4.08	1.29	1	7
Activism intentions	3.81	1.27	1	7
Radicalism intentions	2.75	1.42	1	6.6
Affective polarisation	6.05	2.15	1	10

Table 1. Descriptive statistics ($N = 245$)

5.1.1.2 Associations Between Exposure, Susceptibility Factors, and Outcomes

Bivariate correlations among study variables are shown in Figure 1. Hateful migration exposure was positively associated with activism intentions ($r = .23, p < .001$), radicalism intentions ($r = .18, p < .01$), and stereotype warmth ($r = .17, p < .01$), but was not significantly related to desensitisation or affective polarisation. Political orientation was strongly related to several outcomes, including desensitisation ($r = .50, p < .001$) and stereotype warmth ($r = -.43, p < .001$). The susceptibility variables also showed meaningful intercorrelations, with SPS positively related to activism and radicalism intentions, and CFS and RWA showing distinct patterns across outcomes. Overall, correlations were moderate in size, suggesting that multicollinearity is unlikely to bias regression estimates.

Correlations among key study variables

Lower triangle shown; cells display Pearson correlations with significance stars

Figure 1. Correlations among study variables. The heatmap displays bivariate Pearson correlations among all variables. Colours indicate the direction and strength of associations, and only the lower triangle is shown for readability.

5.1.1.3 Exposure and Individual Characteristics as Predictors of Outcomes

Regression analyses examined whether self-reported exposure to hateful migration-related content was associated with key outcomes among Italian young adults while adjusting for age, gender, education, political orientation, immigration background, SES, sensory processing sensitivity (SPS), cognitive flexibility (CFS), and right-wing authoritarianism (RWA). As shown in Figure 1, greater hateful migration exposure was associated with more positive stereotype warmth, $b = 0.09$, $p = .05$, stronger activism intentions, $b = 0.14$, $p = .003$, and stronger radicalism intentions, $b = 0.15$, $p = .005$. The association with desensitisation was only marginal, $b = 0.07$, $p = .072$, and no significant associations were found for affective polarisation. Full model estimates are reported in Appendix Table C1.

The adjusted models also indicated that several susceptibility-related characteristics were linked to outcomes. A more right-wing political orientation was associated with greater desensitisation, $b = 0.19$, $p < .001$, less positive stereotype competence, $b = -0.11$, $p = .006$, less positive stereotype warmth, $b = -0.20$, $p < .001$, lower activism intentions, $b = -0.17$, $p < .001$, and higher affective polarisation, $b = 0.19$, $p = .008$. Higher SPS was associated with more positive stereotype competence, $b = 0.24$, $p = .007$, more positive stereotype warmth, $b = 0.17$, $p = .045$, stronger activism intentions, $b = 0.34$, $p < .001$, and stronger radicalism intentions, $b = 0.26$, $p = .007$. Higher CFS was associated

with lower desensitisation, $b = -0.30, p = .005$, more positive stereotype warmth, $b = 0.28, p = .021$, and lower radicalism intentions, $b = -0.52, p < .001$. Higher RWA was associated with greater desensitisation, $b = 0.29, p < .001$, stronger radicalism intentions, $b = 0.32, p = .001$, and lower affective polarisation, $b = -0.41, p = .007$. In addition, women reported lower desensitisation, $b = -0.35, p = .015$, and lower radicalism intentions, $b = -0.50, p = .006$.

Figure 2. Standardised regression coefficients across outcomes. Points represent standardised coefficients from regression models, and horizontal lines indicate 95% confidence intervals. Filled points denote statistically significant effects ($p < .05$). Panels correspond to different outcome variables.

5.1.1.4 Susceptibility as a Moderator: Does Individual Vulnerability Amplify Exposure Effects?

Building on the main effect analyses, a series of moderation models were estimated to examine whether individual susceptibility characteristics amplify the impact of hateful content exposure. Sensory processing sensitivity (SPS), cognitive flexibility (CFS), and right-wing authoritarianism (RWA) were selected as moderators on theoretical grounds, reflecting core differences in emotional reactivity, cognitive control, and dispositional receptivity to extreme content respectively. All continuous variables were mean-centred prior to analysis.

A significant interaction between hateful content exposure and right-wing authoritarianism emerged in predicting radicalism intentions ($b = 0.12, p = .011$). Simple slopes analysis revealed that the effect of exposure was non-significant among individuals low in RWA ($b = 0.04, p = .56$), significant at mean levels of RWA ($b = 0.17, p < .01$), and strongest among those high in RWA ($b = 0.29, p < .001$). This suggests that right-wing authoritarianism is a meaningful susceptibility factor that amplifies the

relationship between SUED exposure and radicalism intentions, while individuals low in authoritarianism appear relatively resilient to this effect.

Moderator	Outcome	Interaction <i>b</i>	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Significant
RWA	Radicalism	0.12	0.05	2.55	.011	✓
CFS	Radicalism	-0.07	0.08	-0.94	.349	✗
RWA	Desensitisation	0.03	0.04	0.78	.434	✗
SPS	Radicalism	-0.03	0.05	-0.52	.602	✗
SPS	Activism	-0.01	0.05	-0.24	.813	✗

Table 2. The interaction coefficients for all tested moderation models.

Note. *b* = unstandardised interaction coefficient. All models adjusted for age, gender, education, political orientation, migration background, contact, SES, and remaining susceptibility variables.

5.1.2 Adolescents

5.1.2.1 Variable overview

Before the intervention, adolescents' levels of involvement in hate speech were already low. Mean scores suggest that perpetration ($M = 2.04$) was low and victimisation ($M = 1.45$) even lower. Defending others was more common but still below the scale midpoint ($M = 2.65$). Although engagement in hate speech online was low, variations within that low range are still important as they can help identify those who are more susceptible to extreme discourse. The descriptive data of study variables is shown in Table 3.

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>min</i>	<i>max</i>
Online hate speech involvement - defending	2.65	1.12	1	5
Online hate speech involvement - perpetration	2.04	1.33	1	5
Online hate speech involvement - victimisation	1.45	.8	1	4
Counter speech	3	.88	1	5
Critical reflection skills	2.81	.62	1.2	4
Empathy	3.16	.82	1	4.83
Environmental sensitivity (SPS)	4.41	.73	2.42	6.42
Factual hate speech knowledge	3.2	.77	1	5
Media literacy	3.69	.69	1.83	5
Self-efficacy	2.48	.65	1	4
Sense of responsibility	1.43	.79	0	3

Table 3. Descriptive statistics ($N = 151$)

5.1.2.2 Associations Between Exposure, Individual Factors and Responses to Hate Speech

The analysis of pretest data yielded no significant correlations between hate speech perpetration and the individual variables measured, as can be seen in Figure 3. Furthermore, the general level of perpetration was low. Higher victimisation was associated with two individual factors: increased levels of empathy ($r = .21, p = .012$) and higher counter speech ($r = .26, p = .001$). Defending others was the form of hate speech involvement correlated most consistently and theoretically meaningfully with individual factors. Higher levels of defending were positively associated with empathy ($r = .247, p = .002$), self-efficacy ($r = .239, p = .003$), responsibility ($r = .201, p = .014$), media literacy ($r = .172, p = .035$), and factual knowledge ($r = .184, p = .023$).

While victimisation and defending were correlated with a number of competencies, it proved more difficult to identify risk factors for becoming involved in hate speech exacerbating the development of prevention or intervention measures. This difficulty may be explained by adolescents engaged in hate speech not clearly fitting into one distinct role of perpetrators, victims, or defenders. Instead, they were more likely to be involved overall, in any role. The three forms of hate speech involvement being related to each other, particularly victimisation and defending being moderately positively correlated ($r = .356, p < .001$), supports this interpretation.

Figure 3. Correlation heatmap of pre-test variables and online hate speech involvement.

5.2 Susceptibility to Intervention Measures in Adolescence

The HateLess pilot intervention showed preliminary positive effects, particularly in terms of cognitive outcomes. Factual hate speech knowledge increased significantly among the students who received the intervention ($b = .60, p < .001, partial\ eta^2 = .16$). They also displayed an improvement in media literacy ($b = .30, p = .001, partial\ eta^2 = .10$). Additionally, students who participated in the programme reported less hate speech victimisation at post-test ($b = -.27, p = .05, confidence\ interval = -.54\ to\ .001$). However, the effect size was small. These findings provide preliminary evidence that the adapted HateLess intervention may improve selected cognitive competencies, especially factual knowledge and media literacy. As regards moderation analyses, we focused on SPS and empathy in relation to the main outcomes of the intervention. Results of these regression analyses are shown in Table 4.

Moderator	Outcome	b	SE	t	p
SPS	Media literacy skills	-.244	.125	-1.948	.053
SPS	Factual knowledge	-.250	.146	-1.710	.089
SPS	Critical reflection	-.045	.105	-.425	.672
Empathy	Media literacy skills	.153	.112	1.371	.172
Empathy	Factual knowledge	.069	.128	.544	.587

Empathy	Critical reflection	-.199	.097	-2.065	.041
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Table 4. Interaction coefficients for moderation models

Note. $N = 151$. $b =$ unstandardised interaction coefficient. SPS = sensory processing sensitivity.

The following section first presents the theoretically motivated moderation analyses involving SPS and empathy. Additional exploratory subgroup analyses are reported separately below to avoid treating all moderation effects as equivalent. A marginally significant interaction effect of condition and SPS on students' media literacy skills emerged. Follow-up simple slopes analysis indicated that the intervention effect on media literacy skills was strongest among students with lower levels of environmental sensitivity ($b = .48, p < .001$), remained significant at mean levels of SPS ($b = .30, p = .001$), and was no longer significant among students with higher levels of SPS ($b = .12, p = .33$). This pattern may indicate that students with lower environmental sensitivity had more room to benefit in terms of media literacy. However, as the interaction was only marginally significant, this interpretation should be treated as tentative.

A significant condition x empathy interaction effect was also found. Simple slope analysis revealed that the intervention effect on critical reflection was not significant among students with low empathy ($b = .10, p = .33$) or at mean levels of empathy ($b = -.07, p = .40$). Among students with higher levels of empathy (+1 SD), the intervention was associated with lower levels of critical reflection compared to the control condition ($b = -.23, p = .024$). This effect suggests that the intervention may have been less impactful for students who already possessed higher empathetic dispositions, possibly because these students were already more inclined to critically reflect on issues related to hate speech and social responsibility. However, this cannot be concluded incontestably from the present pilot data, and this finding should be considered exploratory.

Figure 4. Moderation effects of the HateLess intervention across identity, background, and prior hate speech involvement

Additional exploratory analyses suggested that some intervention-related gains varied by gender, background, and prior hate speech involvement (see Figure 4). Regarding gender, empathy increased significantly more between pre- and post-test among boys than girls ($b = .44, p = .027$). Due to the small sample size of gender-diverse participants, their responses cannot reliably be included in this analysis.

Students' background was also associated with some differential intervention outcomes. Among students who migrated to Italy or whose parents did, the intervention led to a higher increase in sense of responsibility for intervening in hate speech incidents compared to those without an immigrant background ($b = .44, p = .044$). Additionally, family affluence negatively interacted with self-efficacy ($b = -.20, p = .046$) indicating that the HateLess programme strengthened self-efficacy among participants from a lower economic background in particular. It is important to note here that immigrant background and family affluence were moderately negatively correlated ($r = -.26$) implying that the intervention may have been especially effective among adolescents positioned at the intersection of migration-related and socioeconomic vulnerability. These findings are particularly relevant in respect to equity and the DEMINE context. Nevertheless, the moderation effects remain analytically distinct and these patterns should be interpreted cautiously because the analyses were exploratory and the sample size was limited.

Another factor in individual intervention susceptibility was hate speech involvement prior to the intervention. Participants who indicated higher perpetration frequency at pre-test profited notably from the intervention in terms of self-efficacy ($b = .23, p = .021$). Responsibility toward intervening in hate speech incidents particularly rose among those who reported a higher prevalence of being victims of hate speech ($b = .22, p = .034$). Thus, the intervention seems to have been especially beneficial to adolescents already involved more strongly in hate speech dynamics. These exploratory findings suggest that adolescents already involved in hate speech dynamics may have shown particular gains in self-efficacy or responsibility, but further research is needed to confirm this pattern.

Taken together, these findings are broadly consistent with theoretical perspectives on individual susceptibility to environmental influences (Pluess, 2015). In the present case, however, the observed pattern more closely resembles a compensatory effect, whereby the intervention appears to yield greater benefits for students with lower initial susceptibility-related dispositions. In other words, students who were initially less predisposed to attend to social and emotional cues (e.g., lower SPS) or less inclined to engage in empathetic processing may have had more room to benefit from the programme's learning activities, whereas students who already possessed higher levels of these dispositions may have experienced smaller gains because they were already relatively attentive to or reflective about issues related to hate speech and social responsibility. Nevertheless, the moderation and subgroup findings should be interpreted as preliminary evidence of differential responsiveness rather than definitive evidence of susceptibility profiles. The strongest conclusions concern the overall improvements in factual hate speech knowledge and media literacy. Findings involving interaction effects are useful for generating hypotheses for the main study, but should not be overinterpreted given the pilot design, non-randomised classroom assignment, and limited statistical power.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Susceptibility to extreme discourse among young people

Taken together, the results show nuances in the effects of exposure to hateful content online. Among young adults, exposure was consistently associated with stronger radicalism and activism intentions on the immigration issue even after adjusting for a broad range of sociodemographic factors. However, these associations should be interpreted with caution given that exposure was self-reported, meaning the measure likely captures *recognised* hateful content rather than objective exposure. Recognition itself may be shaped by prior attitudes and sensitivity, individuals more positively disposed toward migrants may be more attuned to identifying content as hateful, while desensitised individuals may over time perceive the same content as less extreme and therefore underreport their exposure. This is an inherent limitation of cross-sectional self-report data, and longitudinal or digital trace studies are better positioned to address.

Individual differences in susceptibility of young adults nonetheless emerged as meaningful predictors of outcomes. Right-wing authoritarianism, reflecting orientations toward discipline, authority, and law enforcement, amplified the relationship between hateful content exposure and radicalism intentions, identifying high-RWA young adults as a particularly vulnerable group to radicalise. Cognitive flexibility, reflecting the capacity to consider multiple perspectives and adapt behaviour across situations, was independently associated with lower desensitisation to hateful migration content, suggesting that more cognitively flexible individuals are less likely to become emotionally numbed to hostile portrayals of migrants even without directly moderating exposure effects.

Sensory processing sensitivity, capturing deep environmental awareness, emotional reactivity, and susceptibility to overwhelm, was independently associated with both stronger activism and radicalism intentions among young adults, yet showed no relationship with desensitisation toward migration-specific content. This is a genuinely puzzling pattern: the absence of a desensitisation link rules out general emotional reactivity as an explanation. Although motivational factors such as prior interest or issue importance may contribute to activism and radicalism intentions, their role remains uncertain, as such factors were not directly assessed. This finding warrants closer examination in future longitudinal waves.

The findings of the HateLess pilot study indicate that the hate speech involvement of participating adolescents was low but still offered meaningful insight that can inform intervention efforts. While it did limit measurability and variation preventing the identification of perpetration predictors, individual factors correlating with victimisation and particularly defending could still be determined.

Regarding perpetration, the most likely explanation for the lack of correlations is the low overall perpetration score allowing for little variation, limiting the measurability and statistical analysis of correlations. Nevertheless, this is not indicative of an absence of predictors but of a measurement limitation. Additionally, the social stigma associated with being a perpetrator may lead to students underreporting their behaviour limiting variation further. Perpetration might also be determined more by situational catalysts, e.g., peer behaviour or conflict, than by fixed traits such as sensitivity or knowledge. Further research is required to provide factual reasoning for this occurrence. The lack of meaningful correlations likely does not signify an actual absence of predictors but is rather to be ascribed to restrictions in measurability and analysis exacerbating the understanding of perpetration susceptibility with self-report data.

The correlation of higher victimisation with higher empathy and counter speech suggests that personal experience as a target of hate speech may increase harm sensitivity and active response likelihood. However, heightened awareness, increased reporting tendencies and personal experience might have a larger influence on these correlations than direct causation. Several underlying elements may cause the correlation between victimisation and empathy. First, personal experience with being a target of hate speech may heighten one's sensitivity to others' suffering. Second, more empathetic adolescents may be more capable of detecting hate speech and understand its harm. Third, these individuals may be more inclined to disclose such experiences. Victimisation was further associated with counter speech suggesting that students who become victims of hate speech actively oppose it more frequently, for instance, as a response or coping strategy. Overall, victimisation is significantly correlated with empathy and counter speech indicating that adolescents' own experiences with hate speech enhance their sensitivity to harmful discourse and proactive countering behaviour. Nevertheless, alternative interpretations, for instance, variations in exposure and awareness, should be explored.

Defending behaviour yielded the strongest correlation pattern. The correlation between defending behaviour and empathy corresponds to previous findings that increased sensitivity to others' well-being amplifies the likelihood of interfering. The positive correlation between self-efficacy, responsibility and defending reinforces this finding. Greater self-efficacy and perceived responsibility are associated with a higher likelihood of intervening in hate speech. Cognitive factors such as social media literacy and factual hate speech knowledge are also positively correlated with defending behaviour. While students with more media literacy and factual knowledge might spend more time online, these competencies might enable them to better detect and interpret hate speech. Thus, they might be more likely to intervene and to feel more justified doing so. These factors can be linked to broader educational influences, such as having adults who explain issues and foster digital autonomy. Defending others who become targets of hate speech seems to be strengthened by both emotional and cognitive competencies. Therefore, it is fundamental to develop a combination of skills and attitudes for successfully fostering defending behaviour. Its association with emotional (empathy), cognitive (media literacy, factual knowledge), and motivational (sense of responsibility, self-efficacy) aspects implies that proactively defending others from hate speech is primarily dictated by a combination of morality, skills and confidence. Thus, these skills can be learned, making this finding relevant for informing prevention strategies

6.2 Susceptibility to Intervention Measures in Adolescence

The HateLess pilot intervention showed promising preliminary effects in fostering selected competencies relevant to hate speech prevention, particularly factual knowledge and media literacy. Results also indicated that it was more efficacious among certain groups of participants, but these patterns require confirmation in a larger and more rigorous study. Media literacy tended to increase among adolescents with low environmental sensitivity, while those with higher levels of empathy displayed limited growth in terms of critical reflection skills, potentially due to the high levels at baseline. Individual characteristics played a key role in intervention outcomes. For example, boys, participants with an immigrant background, students from lower-affluence families, and adolescents with prior hate speech involvement showed stronger gains on selected outcomes. While relevant from an equity perspective, it should be interpreted cautiously.

6.3 Overall conclusion and recommendations

Combining the findings of the two studies, susceptibility to extreme discourse among young people cannot be characterised by one singular risk profile. Instead, it develops as varying reaction patterns influenced by individual traits, past experiences and social environments. In young adults, susceptibility was mainly shaped by how exposure to migration-related harmful discourse was linked to attitudinal and behavioural intentions, especially high levels of right-wing authoritarianism. Among adolescents, hate speech involvement was higher in those with certain competencies likely developed by past experience with hate speech, but individuals could not be categorised as perpetrators, victims, or defenders based on risk factors. However, their traits and identity affected their susceptibility to intervention effectiveness offering insights for future intervention methods. Taken together, the findings suggest that individual differences may shape vulnerability to hate speech as a form of extreme discourse and receptiveness to prevention measures.

Among young adults, the findings point in two complementary directions regarding intervention design. For high-RWA young adults, reducing exposure to hateful content is likely an impractical target, but interventions should be designed to engage rather than alienate more conservative viewpoints. Counter-narrative approaches that acknowledge legitimate concerns around migration, rather than framing all critical discourse as hateful, are more likely to resonate across the dispositional spectrum. Separately, cognitive flexibility represents a promising and trainable target. Perspective-taking exercises and media literacy programmes aimed at broadening interpretive repertoires may help reduce desensitisation to hateful migration content across the broader young adult population, regardless of individual disposition.

The second study's findings indicate that future interventions should continue to impart knowledge, while training critical competencies taking into consideration individual differences. As the involvement type with the strongest associations, prevention programmes should particularly strengthen defending-related skills such as self-efficacy and media literacy. If feasible, adapting certain intervention aspects to student profiles and structural vulnerabilities could further increase intervention success and promote equity.

Taken together, these findings suggest that effective prevention requires a dual approach that combines engagement with individuals' existing beliefs and the strengthening of protective competencies. While interventions for young adults may benefit from emphasising inclusive communication strategies and cognitive flexibility, approaches targeting adolescents should prioritise skill development and supportive environments. Across both groups, accounting for individual differences and contextual factors appears crucial for maximising intervention effectiveness and promoting equitable outcomes.

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8. Appendices

A. Measurement Items Study 1

A1. Exposure to Hateful Immigration-Related Content

Exposure was measured with a single item adapted from Soral et al. (2018):

- “How often do you see hateful or hostile content on social media about immigrants, migrants, or refugees?”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = never, 7 = very often).

A2. Desensitisation to Hate

Desensitisation was measured using four items:

- “Seeing hateful comments about immigrants on social media doesn’t really bother me.”
- “When I come across hateful comments about immigrants online, I don’t have much of an emotional reaction.”
- “I feel upset when I see hateful comments about immigrants on social media.” (reverse-coded)
- “Hateful or degrading posts about immigrants don’t seem very serious or harmful to me.”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree).

A3. Stereotypes Toward Immigrants

Stereotypes were measured using a 6-item scale (Asbrock, 2010), capturing two dimensions:

- Competence (“Immigrants are competent/competitive/independent.”)
- Warmth (“Immigrants are likeable/warm/good-natured.”)

Participants indicated how much each statement reflected their personal perception of immigrants on a 7-point scale (1 = not at all, 7 = completely).

A4. Activism and Radicalism Intentions

Activism and radicalism intentions were measured using an adapted version of the Activism and Radicalism Intention Scale (ARIS; Moskalenko & McCauley, 2009). The scale is composed of two subscales: the Activism Intention Scale (AIS) and the Radicalism Intention Scale (RIS). The AIS assesses an individual’s readiness to support or take part in legal and non-violent behaviour in the name of a group or organization, while the RIS assesses an individual’s readiness to support and participate in illegal and violent behaviour in the name of a group or organization

Items include:

- I would join or belong to an organization that works to advance my position on the immigration issue.
- I would donate money to an organization working to advance my position on the immigration issue.
- I would volunteer time (e.g., petitions, flyers, recruitment) for an organization working on immigration issues aligned with my views.

- I would travel for one hour to join a rally or public event related to the immigration position I support.
- I would support an immigration-related organization aligned with my views even if it sometimes breaks the law.
- I would support such an organization even if it sometimes resorts to violence in pursuing its goals on immigration issues.
- I would participate in a protest related to immigration where there is a possibility that violence might occur.
- I would use violence against police or security forces if I saw them using force against people on my side of the immigration issue.
- I would go to war to defend the immigration policy position I support.
- I would retaliate against a group that used violence against those who share my immigration-related views, even if I wasn't sure I was retaliating against the guilty parties.

All items were measured on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree).

A5. Contact with Immigrants

Contact with immigrants was measured with two items:

- "How often do you personally have contact with people with a migration background from other European countries?"
- "How often do you personally have contact with people with a migration background from non-European countries?"

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale: (1 = never, 5 = every day).

A6. Immigration background

Immigration background was measured using two items:

- "Were you born in [country]?"
- "Were your parents born in [country]?"

Response options for the first item were: (1 = yes, 2 = no, born abroad). Response options for the second item were: (1 = both parents born in [country], 2 = one parent born abroad, 3 = both parents born abroad).

A7. Household Financial Situation (SES)

Household financial situation was measured with a single item:

"Which of the following best describes your financial situation and that of the people you live with?"

Response options were:

- "We live very well – We can purchase luxury items and still have money left over."
- "We live well – We can afford most things without needing to save for them."
- "We get by fine – We have enough for everyday needs but must save for larger expenses."
- "We live modestly – We must manage money carefully and limit daily spending."

- “We struggle to get by – We sometimes cannot afford basic needs such as food or clothing.”

A8. Political Orientation

Political orientation was measured using a single self-placement item:

- “In politics, people sometimes talk about left and right. Where would you place yourself on this scale?”

Responses were recorded on an 11-point scale (0 = left, 10 = right).

A9. Cognitive Flexibility

Cognitive flexibility was measured using the 12-item Cognitive Flexibility Scale (Martin & Rubin, 1995).

Items include:

- “I can communicate an idea in many different ways.”
- “I avoid new and unusual situations.” (reverse-coded)
- “I feel like I never get to make decisions.” (reverse-coded)
- “I can find workable solutions to seemingly unsolvable problems.”
- “I seldom have choices when deciding how to behave.” (reverse-coded)
- “I am willing to work at creative solutions to problems.”
- “In any given situation, I am able to act appropriately.”
- “My behaviour is a result of conscious decisions that I make.”
- “I have many possible ways of behaving in any given situation.”
- “I have difficulty using my knowledge on a given topic in real-life situations.” (reverse-coded)
- “I am willing to listen and consider alternatives for handling a problem.”
- “I have the self-confidence necessary to try different ways of behaving.”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree).

A10. Sensory Processing Sensitivity

Sensory processing sensitivity was measured using a 12-item short scale (Pluess et al., 2023; based on Aron & Aron, 1997).

Participants were instructed to answer each question according to how they personally feel. Items include:

- “Do you seem to be aware of subtleties in your environment?”
- “Are you easily overwhelmed by things like bright lights, strong smells, coarse fabrics, or sirens close by?”
- “Do you have a rich, complex inner life?”
- “Do you get rattled when you have a lot to do in a short amount of time?”
- “Are you deeply moved by the arts or music?”
- “Are you annoyed when people try to get you to do too many things at once?”
- “Do you make a point to avoid violent movies and TV shows?”
- “Do you find it unpleasant to have a lot going on at once?”
- “Do changes in your life shake you up?”

- “Do you notice and enjoy delicate or fine scents, tastes, sounds, works of art?”
- “Are you bothered by intense stimuli, like loud noises or chaotic scenes?”
- “When you must compete or be observed while performing a task, do you become so nervous or shaky that you do much worse than you would otherwise?”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = not at all, 7 = completely).

A12. Right-Wing Authoritarianism

Right-wing authoritarianism was measured using the Very Short RWA scale (Bizumic & Duckitt, 2018).

Items include:

- It's great that many young people today are prepared to defy authority. (reverse-coded)
- What our country needs most is discipline, with everyone following our leaders in unity.
- God's laws about abortion, pornography, and marriage must be strictly followed before it is too late.
- There is nothing wrong with premarital sexual intercourse. (reverse-coded)
- Our society does NOT need tougher government and stricter laws. (reverse-coded)
- The facts on crime and recent public disorders show we have to crack down harder on troublemakers, if we are going to preserve law and order.

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree).

A13. Affective Polarisation

Affective polarisation was measured using a feeling thermometer item:

- “How sympathetic are you toward people who hold different views on the migration issue?”

Responses were recorded on a 10-point scale (1 = not at all sympathetic, 10 = very sympathetic) and reversed for analysis so that higher score indicates higher affective polarisation.

B. Questionnaire Study 2

The questionnaire was primarily completed individually on students’ smartphones. Paper-based versions were provided on request. While most students used the Italian version, the questionnaire was also available in Albanian, English, Mandarin, Romanian, and Ukrainian. The below questionnaire is the English-language online version to ensure accessibility.

B1. Well-being

Well-being was measured using the WHO-5 Well-Being Index (World Health Organization, 1998).

Items are:

- “I have felt cheerful and in good spirits.”
- “I have felt calm and relaxed.”
- “I have felt active and energetic.”
- “I woke up feeling fresh and rested.”
- “My daily life has been filled with things that interest me.”

Responses were recorded on a 6-point scale (1 = never, 6 = always).

B2. Self-esteem

Self-esteem was measured using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg, 1979).

Items are:

- “In general, I am satisfied with myself.”
- “I feel that I have several good qualities.”
- “I am capable of doing things at least as well as most people.”
- “Sometimes I feel completely useless.” (reverse-coded)
- “I feel that I am worth at least as much as others.”
- “I would like to have more respect for myself.” (reverse-coded)
- “Overall, I tend to believe that I am a failure.” (reverse-coded)
- “I have a positive attitude towards myself.”
- “Every now and then I think I'm worthless.” (reverse-coded)
- “I feel like I don't have much to be proud of.” (reverse-coded)

Responses were recorded on a 4-point scale (1 = not at all, 4 = very much).

B3. Environmental Sensitivity

Environmental sensitivity was measured using the Highly Sensitive Child Scale (Pluess et al., 2017).

Items are:

- “I notice it when small things have changed in my environment.”
- “Loud noises make me feel uncomfortable.”
- “I love nice smells.”
- “I get nervous when I have to do a lot in little time.”
- “Some music can make me really happy.”
- “I am annoyed when people try to get me to do too many things at once.”
- “I find it unpleasant to have a lot going on at once.”
- “I love nice tastes.”
- “When someone observes me, I get nervous.”
- “I don't like watching TV programmes that have a lot of violence in them.”
- “I don't like it when things change in my life.”
- “I don't like loud noises.”

Responses were recorded on a 7-point scale (1 = not at all, 7 = very much).

B4. Media Literacy

Media literacy was measured using the “Subjective Social Media Literacy” subscale of the Youth Social Media Literacy Scale (Purinton Drake et al., 2023).

Items are:

- “I know how to spot ads on social media.”
- “I know what cyberbullying is.”
- “I know how long things posted on social media stay there.”
- “I know what fake news is.”

- “I know how to spot scams on social media.”
- “I know what I can do if social media makes me feel worried, sad, or anxious.”

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale (1 = not at all, 5 = very much).

B5. Factual Hate Speech Knowledge

Factual hate speech knowledge was measured using a scale by Wachs et al. (2024).

Items are:

- “I know what hate speech is.”
- “I know the causes of hate speech.”
- “I know the consequences of hate speech.”
- “I know what I can do when someone is the victim of hate speech.”
- “I know how I can cope when I am the victim of hate speech.”
- “I know who I can turn to when I am the victim of hate speech.”

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale (1 = not at all, 5 = very much).

B6. Openness to Diversity

Openness to diversity was measured using a scale by Özdemir et al. (2020).

Items are:

- “I accept and am open to people who are very different from me.”
- “I feel comfortable talking to people with very different opinions.”
- “I am open to others who have different ways of doing things.”
- “I treat everyone equally, even if they are different from me.”

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale (1 = not at all, 5 = very much).

B7. Critical Reflection

Critical reflection was measured using the Critical Reflection Scale (Chan, 2022).

Items are:

- “I believe that all people are treated equally.”
- “I believe people get what they deserve.”
- “I think that education gives everyone an equal chance.”
- “I believe that the world is basically fair.”
- “I think all social groups are respected.”

Responses were recorded on a 4-point scale (1 = not at all, 4 = very much).

B8. Online Hate Speech Involvement

Online hate speech involvement was measured using items by Wachs et al. (2024).

Items are:

- “On the internet, I perpetrate hate speech.”
- “On the internet, I defend others who become targets of hate speech.”

- “On the internet, I become the target of hate speech.”

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale (1 = never, 5 = always).

B9. Empathy

Empathy was measured using a scale by Knauf et al. (2018), adapted by Wachs et al. (2023).

Items are:

- “It affects me deeply.”
- “It hurts me, too.”
- “I realise how badly the affected person is doing.”
- “I can imagine how bad it must be.”
- “I’m full of compassion.”
- “I feel the need to protect or comfort the person.”

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale (1 = not at all, 5 = very much).

B10. Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy was measured using a scale by Knauf et al. (2018).

Items are:

- “I know that there are things I can do.”
- “I can think of ways to act.”
- “I have ideas how I can help.”

Responses were recorded on a 4-point scale (1 = not at all, 4 = very much).

B11. Sense of Responsibility

Sense of responsibility was measured using a scale by Knauf et al. (2018).

Items are:

- “I’m ashamed if I don’t take action.”
- “I believe it’s my responsibility.”
- “I feel guilty if I do nothing.”

Responses were recorded on a 4-point scale (1 = not at all, 4 = very much).

B12. Counter Speech

Counter speech was measured using a scale by Wachs et al. (2023).

Items are:

- “I tell the person such statements are hurtful.”
- “I ask the person to stop.”
- “I ask questions to make them think.”
- “I point out false information.”

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale (1 = not at all, 5 = very much).

B13. Academic Engagement

Academic engagement was measured using the Engagement vs. Disaffection with Learning Scale (Skinner et al., 2008).

Items are:

- “I listen very carefully.”
- “I enjoy learning new things.”
- “I participate in discussions.”
- “I try hard to do well.”
- “I feel interested in class.”

Responses were recorded on a 4-point scale (1 = not at all, 4 = very much).

B14. Classroom Climate

Classroom climate was measured using a scale by Özdemiş et al. (2020).

Items are:

- “We help each other in my class.”
- “We are nice to each other.”
- “We like to do things together.”
- “No one feels left out.”

Responses were recorded on a 5-point scale (1 = not at all, 5 = very much).

B15. Socioeconomic Status

Socioeconomic status was measured using the Family Affluence Scale by Currie et al. (2023)

Items are:

- Number of cars
- Own bedroom
- Number of bathrooms
- Number of computers
- Family holidays outside the country
- Dishwasher ownership

Responses were recorded using categorical response options and summed into an index score.

C. Tables

	Desensitisation	Stereotype competence	Stereotype warmth	Activism intentions	Radicalism intentions	Affective polarisation
Exposure to hateful content	0.081* (0.041)	0.069 (0.046)	0.072 (0.046)	0.128** (0.046)	0.152** (0.052)	-0.044 (0.083)
Age	-0.017 (0.039)	0.067 (0.044)	-0.016 (0.044)	0.000 (0.044)	0.058 (0.050)	-0.141 (0.080)

Female	-0.347*	-0.057	-0.035	-0.272	-0.507**	0.345
	(0.143)	(0.160)	(0.159)	(0.159)	(0.181)	(0.290)
Higher education	0.338*	-0.098	0.025	-0.102	0.009	-0.118
	(0.150)	(0.168)	(0.166)	(0.167)	(0.190)	(0.304)
Political orientation	0.188***	-0.100**	-0.198***	-0.169***	-0.079	0.174*
	(0.034)	(0.038)	(0.038)	(0.038)	(0.043)	(0.069)
Immigration background	-0.061	0.181	0.179	0.003	0.124	-0.719
	(0.221)	(0.248)	(0.245)	(0.247)	(0.281)	(0.449)
SES	0.111	0.041	0.042	-0.052	0.023	-0.369*
	(0.081)	(0.091)	(0.090)	(0.090)	(0.103)	(0.164)
Sensory processing sensitivity	0.010	0.234**	0.169*	0.336***	0.269**	-0.207
	(0.077)	(0.087)	(0.086)	(0.086)	(0.098)	(0.157)
Cognitive flexibility	-0.283*	0.135	0.237	0.150	-0.501***	-0.228
	(0.110)	(0.123)	(0.122)	(0.122)	(0.139)	(0.222)
Right-wing authoritarianism	0.285***	-0.059	-0.084	0.043	0.311**	-0.405**
	(0.075)	(0.085)	(0.084)	(0.084)	(0.096)	(0.153)
Constant	2.343*	0.833	3.331**	2.221	1.465	13.058***
	(1.137)	(1.277)	(1.262)	(1.269)	(1.444)	(2.309)
Num.Obs.	245	245	245	245	245	245
R2	0.376	0.140	0.254	0.209	0.185	0.096
R2 Adj.	0.347	0.099	0.218	0.172	0.147	0.053

- p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001

Table C1. Multiple regression models predicting desensitisation, stereotype evaluations, activism intentions, radicalism intentions, and affective polarisation among young adults